

COMPARISON OF SHORT CARBON AND POLY(P-PHENYLENE-2,6-BENZOBISOXAZOLE) FIBERS ON THE PROPERTIES OF POLYESTER THERMOPLASTIC ELASTOMERS

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Introduction to Thermoplastic Elastomers and Fabrication of Composites

Thermoplastic elastomers are an interesting class of materials which combine the benefits of toughness and flexibility of traditional thermosetting rubbers with the processability and ability to be remolded and recycled of thermoplastics [1]. Their interesting combination of properties make them interesting candidates for numerous industrial applications [2].

Poly(p-phenylene-2,6-benzobisoxazole) (PBO) is a high-strength thermosetting polymer with additional benefits of improved abrasion resistance, and excellent fatigue resistance. The comparison of Carbon and PBO fibers is interesting because despite having similar base mechanical properties their resulting composites perform differently.

In this study PBO and Carbon fiber composites using a polyester-based thermoplastic elastomer were tested for their thermal and mechanical properties. Composites were prepared with 5% and 10% by weight for each fiber type

Fiber	Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (GPa)	Pre-Processing length (mm)
PBO	270	5.8	3
Carbon	242	4.1	3

Reinforcing Filler	Fiber Weight %	Fiber Volume %	Nomenclature
PBO	5	3.9	TPEE 5PBO
	10	7.8	TPEE 10PBO
Carbon Fiber	5	3.3	TPEE 5CF
	10	6.8	TPEE 10CF
Neat			TPEE

Hytel 5556 (DuPont) was the selected material used as the matrix for this study. It is a medium hardness, shore D 55, polyester based thermoplastic elastomer with specific gravity of 1.16. PBO fibers, Zylon HM, were provided by Toyobo, and Carbon fibers, Panex 35, were provided by Zoltek. The composites were fabricated by twin screw compounding at 230°C and 50rpm for 10 minutes. Samples for testing were injection molded with a barrel temperature of 230°C and mold temperature of 45°C

Thermal Properties, TGA and DSC

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was conducted using a TGA Q50 (TA Instruments) with a heating rate of 20°C/min to 600°C in a nitrogen atmosphere.

The PBO composites show a higher degradation onset temperature compared to the neat material while the carbon composites are lower, which indicates superior thermal stability for the PBO reinforce materials.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed using a DSC Q2000 (TA Instruments) between -80°C to 260°C in a nitrogen atmosphere.

Both fibers act as very effective nucleating agents as noticed by the dramatic increase in crystallization temperature. The greater heat of fusion for the neat material suggests higher crystallinity, likely indicating that the stiffness of the fibers restrict the size of the crystals.

Material	Tm (°C)	Tc (°C)	Hf (J/g)
TPEE	202.6	149.8	23.8
TPEE 5CF	202.5	171.7	18.0
TPEE 10CF	202.9	172.7	18.4
TPEE 5PBO	203.9	176.8	20.2
TPEE 10PBO	204.3	180.4	20.9

Mechanical Properties in Tension

The tensile properties were performed on an Instron 5848 Universal Testing Machine. The samples were tested with a strain rate of 5mm/min at room temperature and humidity. The samples show very high elongation to break with the exception of the 10wt% PBO composite which exhibit more brittle failure. While each fiber type provides similar tensile modulus for a given weight fraction the PBO composites have much greater yield strength.

It is hypothesized that a combination of fiber length and adhesion between the fiber and matrix contribute to the greater strength of the PBO composites. The longer fiber length of the PBO fibers results in a greater portion of the load transferred to the fibers compared to the relatively short Carbon fibers.

It is also suggested that the adhesion between the PBO fibers and the elastomeric matrix may be superior as evidenced by the greater yield strength and the lower yield strain. Both of these effects would be prominent in high load conditions and would not affect the modulus which is determined in low force, low strain conditions.

Conclusions and Future Work

- Both carbon and PBO provide excellent reinforcement in terms of modulus to the elastomeric matrix
- Hypothesized that a combination of fiber length and interfacial adhesion result in superior strength of PBO fiber reinforced composites
- Due to being ductile in nature there is much less fiber breakage during processing in the PBO fibers resulting in longer fiber length
- Future work is to investigate the interfacial properties for both fiber types as well as the 3D fiber structure

Fiber Length Investigation

TGA was used to burn off the matrix material of a molded samples leaving the fibers as residue. For the carbon fiber composites, the material was heated to 900°C while the PBO composites were heated to 500°C and held for 30 minutes. The fiber remnants were then imaged by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL JSM-IT100). The PBO fibers were found to be much longer than the carbon fibers for a similarly loaded sample.

Being ductile in nature the PBO fibers are much less susceptible to breakage in the compounding and molding processes and the polymeric and tough behavior of these fibers save them in these high shear processes.